

THE IMPORTANCE OF CHEMISTRY IN INDUSTRY AND THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.

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Annotation: This article discusses the importance of chemistry in industry and the national economy, as well as their application in industries.

Keywords: Chemical industry, plastics, mineral fertilizers, diffraction, atmosphere.

The emergence and development of chemistry goes back to ancient times. Like all Sciences, the science of chemistry has evolved in stages. today, the importance of chemistry in industry and the national economy is great. After the introduction of chemistry, the convenience of working in several areas was created. For example, in the chemical industry, plastic, lacquer materials from chemical fibers and threads began to be produced. several items began to be produced in factories and factories. The chemical industry is one of the heavy sectors and is of great importance in both agriculture and industrial technology. In the national economy, mineral fertilizers are widely used in the chemical industry.

This, in turn, allows our farmers to make the harvest much more efficient and high-quality. Mineral fertilizers were used not only by our farmers, but also by each of us in rural life, and we know how effective it will be. In turn, along with fertilizers, we widely use chemicals and medicines in agriculture. They are mainly used to destroy pests, as well as weeds: only in the national economy, mineral fertilizers and chemicals should be used in their place and in moderation, otherwise our main crop will dry out both trees and further worsen the land. In Agriculture, cotton is widely used in pollination and diffraction of chemical preparations, and it is considered much more effective.

In turn, with the development of the chemical industry, our factories are also increasing. For example, several of our factories were built, such as Chirchik electro combine, Fergana nitrogen fertilizer plant, Samarkand chemical plant, Kokand superfasfod plant, Navoiyazot Open Joint Stock Company. They produce a number of chemical products, but toxic substances from them also affect the atmosphere. This in turn causes several diseases in humans. For example, it will be difficult for people with asthma.

In subsequent years, we need not only to develop the chemical industry, but also to reduce the toxic substances that release it into the atmosphere, since the importance of chemistry in industry and the national economy is significant and important.

Since the 8th century, scientists have done a lot of work on the practice of chemistry. Our scientists, who were famous in that period and even now: Jobr Ibn Khayyam, Central Asian Scientist Farabi, Abu Rayhon Beruni, Musa al-Khorezm, Abu Ali ibn Sina and others, are known all over the world in the field of chemistry. There are more than 150 works by Beruni, and most of them are based on minerals. He determined the specific weights of many elements. They argued that matter is eternal, matter can exist in different forms. In the 17 century, the Irish scientist Robert Boyle: calls simple substances formed from the decomposition of complex substances an element and introduced its true meaning into science.

Famous Russian scientist M. V. Lomonosov showed that the theory of the "flagstone" (a matter of fire) is an erroneous theory. He described his law of 1748 as follows: the more things decrease from one body, the more things are added to the other body, as a result of which the matter decreases so much on one Earth, and in another. This common law of nature also applies to action. This law of Lomonosov is currently called the law of conservation of mass: the mass of reacting substances is equal to the mass of substances formed from the reaction. French scientist A. Lavuaze confirmed Lomonosov's laws through experience. V. M. Lomonosov produced carbon dioxide in 1781 in 10 different ways and found that the ratio between the masses of carbon and oxygen in a gas was 3:8. Based on this, it was concluded that any chemically pure compound, regardless of the extraction method, has an irreplaceable quantitative composition.

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